

Synthesis of a few New 2'-Hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones, 3-Benzoyl-2-arylchromones and 5-Benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-6-aryl-2-thiopyrimidines

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2'-Hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones (2) have been prepared by the condensation of appropriate β -diketone (1) and aromatic aldehyde. The acrylophenones thus obtained were oxidised with SeO_2 to get the respective 3-benzoyl-2-arylchromones (3). These on reaction with thiourea gave 5-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-6-aryl-2-thiopyrimidines (4). The identification of these compounds have been established on the basis of chemical analysis and ir and nmr spectral data.

2-AROYL-3-arylacrylophenones are convenient intermediate for the synthesis of 3-aryl-2-arylchromones¹. They are known for their biological activity². Chromones are found to possess considerable pharmacological properties³. Very diverse range of biological activities are associated with pyrimidine derivatives. In view of these the synthesis of some 2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones, 3-benzoyl-2-arylchromones and 5-benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-6-aryl-2-thiopyrimidines are reported here.

o-Hydroxydibenzoylmethane (1)⁴ was condensed with different aromatic aldehydes to give 2'-hydroxy-2-aryl-3-arylacrylophenones (2a-e). The acrylophenones on oxidative cyclisation with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol gave the corresponding 3-aryl-2-arylchromones (3a-c) which were allowed to react with thiourea in presence of sodium ethoxide to get 2-thiopyrimidines (4a-d) in good yield (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Compounds 2a-e showed ir peaks at 3100-3140 (OH), 1610-1620 (C=C) and 1690-1700 cm^{-1} (C=O). 3 exhibited all characteristic ir features like aryl CO and cyclic CO at 1630-1690 and 1610-1640 cm^{-1} . Absence of a peak at 3200-3400 cm^{-1} (OH) suggests that acrylophenones have undergone oxidation to give the 3-arylchromones.

The 2-thiopyrimidine (4a-d) were obtained by refluxing 3-benzoyl-2-arylchromones with thiourea. Cleavage of γ -pyrone ring occurs and a sulphur-containing compound with free hydroxyl group is generated^{4,6}. These compounds showed the presence of C=S (1620-1630 cm^{-1}) and OH (3060 cm^{-1}) in their ir spectra which agrees with the structure assigned to the compounds.

Experimental

2'-Hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-(4-methylphenyl)acrylophenone (2a): A mixture of ethanol (20 ml), *p*-tolu-aldehyde (1.21 g), *o*-hydroxydibenzoylmethane (2.4 g) and a few drops of piperidine was refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled in an ice-bath. The solid mixture was filtered and crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 114° (Found: C, 80.91; H, 4.92. Requires: C, 80.70; H, 5.26); δ 1.5 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 6.98-8.24 (14H, m, ArH, =CH) and 12.0 (s, OH).

Similarly, other compounds (2b-e) were prepared (Table 1).

3-Benzoyl-2-(4-methylphenyl)chromone (3a): A mixture of isoamyl alcohol (25 ml), 2-benzoyl-3-(4-methylphenyl)acrylophenone (3.42 g) and selenium dioxide (3.33 g) was heated for 12 h, then cooled, filtered and subjected to steam distillation to remove isoamyl alcohol. The residue was extracted with

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2-4*

Compd. no.	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	114	65
2b	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	151	62
2c	3-OCH ₃ ,4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	169	55
2d	4-N.(OH) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	132	65
2e	3,4-OCH ₃ -O-C ₆ H ₄	120	65
3a	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	109	89
3b	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	147	85
3c	3,4-O-OH ₂ -O.C ₆ H ₃	159	55
4a	C ₆ H ₅	79	90
4b	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	91	65
4c	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	131	98
4d	3,4-O-OH ₂ -O.C ₆ H ₃	96	96

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis; in all compounds R=phenyl.

benzene. The extract was washed with cold aqueous sodium carbonate and water and evaporated to dryness to get a solid mass which was crystallised from ethanol, (89%), m.p. 109° (Found: C, 80.88; H, 4.33. Requires: C, 81.17; H, 4.70%); δ 1.5 (s, for CH₃) and 7.25-8.25 (m, ArH).

The oxidative cyclisation was extended to other 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones (Table 1).

5-Benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenyl-2-thiopyrimidine (4a): 3-Benzoylflavone (3, R=R₁=C₆H₅; 1 g) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml). Thiourea (1 g) and a little sodium ethoxide were added to it and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. It was then cooled and poured in water and acidified with HCl. The solid obtained was filtered, washed

with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (66%), m.p. 79° (Found: C, 70.98; H, 4.12; N, 7.32; S, 8.29. Requires: C, 71.87; H, 4.16; N, 7.29; S, 8.33%); δ 1.5 (s, CH₃), 12.12 (s, OH) and 6.90-7.55.

Similarly, other compounds (4a-d) were prepared (Table 1). Raney nickel desulphurisation was observed in all the compounds indicating the presence of acyclic sulphur.

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